

**Primarily
environmental impacts**

1. Collisions with marine mammals and other species
2. Light pollution
3. Wakes and sediment resuspension in shallow waterbodies
4. Other impacts:
 - freshwater withdrawals;
 - construction of port infrastructure;
 - anchoring;
 - Polar/MPA areas impact (wildlife).

**Environmental and related
human health impacts**

1. Solid waste (marine litter, plastics); wastewater (black/grey/bilge water) and ballast water
2. Transfer of species/pathogens
4. Antifouling (biocide) coatings
5. Air pollution: SO_x, NO_x, PMs and air treatment toxic residue
6. Noise pollution
7. Ship dismantling
8. Accidents

**Primarily human
health impacts**

1. Onboard infections: respiratory, gastrointestinal, other (varicella, skin infections, malaria, meningitis)
2. Health issues related to onboard sexual assaults
3. Health issues related to working and living conditions of the crew and workers in shipyards
4. Health and wellbeing impacts related to socio-economic issues

Affected people: Passengers, crew, residents living near cruise ports or dismantling docks, those in the pathways of long range air and marine global pollution, workers in shipyards

Affected environment: air, water (fresh & marine), soil and land cover, sensitive habitats and protected areas, onshore & marine wildlife from near and global pollution & waste deposition